

Effect of Sedentary Life Style on Respiratory Rates and Peak Expiratory Flow Rate among Medical Students

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Abstract

Aim: The current study was undertaken to compare Resting, peak exercise, 5 min after exercise respiratory rates and respiratory rate recovery following Astrand-Ryhming step test and Peak expiratory flow rates (PEFR) between students of Medical Education (ME)).

Material & Methods: The present study was conducted at Government medical college, Bettiah, Bihar, India. The study was conducted on 100 healthy medical students after completion of 1 year of course in the college. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the institutional ethical committee and principal of the college.

Results: The comparison of mean resting, peak exercise, and 5 min after ARST respiratory rates showed that all the differences were statistically highly significant. The increase in respiratory rate at the end of Astrand-Ryhming Step test (ARST) and Percent recovery respiratory rate (Percent RRR) at the end of 5 min recovery after ARST over pre -test between showed significant results. The mean PEFR \pm 1SD in ME students was 460.2 \pm 66.4 and the difference was statistically highly significant.

Conclusion: The present study revealed that the important parameters of pulmonary fitness like Respiratory rates and PEFR among ME students. Beneficial effects of exercise are well known since the ancient Vedas. The present attractive education system has helped to improve the education standards, but the non-active sedentary stressful life has made the youth physically unfit. Regular physical activity is an essential part of the healthy life style and should be encouraged among medical students.

Keywords: Respiratory Rate, PEFR, Medical Education.

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Introduction

Sedentariness is the practice of living in one place for a long time. [1] According to a survey report conducted in 2008, by the United States National Health Survey, 36% of adults are totally inactive while 59% have never participated in vigorous physical activity lasting more than 10

minutes per week. [2] Physical fitness is required not only by athletes for better performance but also by non-athletes for maintenance of physical and mental health. A sedentary lifestyle can contribute to ill health and adverse effects. [1] Physical fitness is required not only by athletes for

better performance but also by non-athletes for maintenance of physical and mental health. Heavy academic workloads in medical schools make it difficult for medical students to maintain a regular exercise program. Physical Education class provides a great variety of activities and high intensity exercises for students. Sedentary living affects people in such a way that it makes them lazy and prone to fatigue. By being inactive muscle tissues are lost which causes muscle atrophy and makes us lose strength, making a person physically weak and fatigue. Aging process can also be accelerated with no physical activity, decreasing the immunity system and giving rise to various diseases. Inadequate physical activity and low levels of fitness in adults contribute to then adequate physical activity and low levels of fitness in adults contribute to the development of obesity, type-2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, the metabolic syndrome, hypercholesterolemia, myocardial infarction, osteoporotic fractures, depression and some cancers. [3] A sedentary lifestyle is the most modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. It is also important for a sedentary population to indulge themselves in regular exercise to maintain proper health as it has been shown that physical inactivity and a negative lifestyle in the sedentary population have seriously threatened the health and it deteriorates the human body. [4]

“Abnormal or excessive accumulation of fats in the body that might be harmful to an individual is termed as obesity. [5] Work done by the World Health Organization shows that global obesity rates have more or less tripled since 1975. As of 2016, more than a third of adults are overweight while nearly a tenth are obese. [6] Obesity is a significant health risk; its prevalence now indicates a near-pandemic. Obesity dramatically heightens the risk of diseases like type II diabetes, myocardial infarction, and various types of cancers. It is thus hazardous to both the quality and

expectancy of life. [7] A multitude of factors such as food habits, lifestyle, and the complicated interactions between genetic, cultural, and socioeconomic forces are all fundamental causes of obesity. [8] Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) is a person's maximum speed of expiration. It measures the airflow through bronchi and thus the degree of obstruction in airways. PEFR is the maximum rate of airflow that can be generated during forced expiratory manoeuvre starting from total lung capacity. It is measured by using a standard Wright Peak Flow meter or mini-Wright meter. [9] Aerobic training is responsible for metabolic adaptations that allow more efficient adjustment of energy expenditure during exercise recovery. [10]

To date there are very few studies evaluating the relationship between sedentary behaviour and pulmonary function in a population who works for more than half a day i.e., 6-8hrs continuously in front of technologies (mainly desk jobs) with no sign of physical activities. Sedentary lifestyles could be associated with less efficient pulmonary functions. Hence, the current study was undertaken to compare important pulmonary fitness parameters between students of Medical Education (ME).

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted at Government medical college, Bettiah, Bihar, India. The study was conducted on 100 healthy medical students after completion of 1 year of course in the college. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the institutional ethical committee.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Healthy male students of medical.
- Aged between 18-25 years after completion of I year study course.

Exclusion Criteria:

Subjects with:

- Cardiovascular diseases
- Respiratory diseases
- Musculoskeletal, Neuromuscular, Endocrine disorders.
- Allergic disorders.
- Alcoholism/smoking habit.
- Chronic infection /disease.
- Acute illness at the time of study.

Methodology

Details of study were explained and a written consent was taken from subjects. All the study parameters in both the groups were recorded during morning hours between 9 am to 11 am at room temperature to avoid any possible diurnal variation effect. Subjects were told to report an hour before experiment. They were asked to refrain from heavy meal or drinking coffee/tea, at least for an hour and allowed to take rest for half an hour before the experiment.

Astrand-Rhything Step test (ARST) [11]: ARST for men requires subjects to step up and down on a 40 cm (16 inch) bench for 5 min at rate of 90 steps/min (22.5 cycles of stepping) or until exhaustion. The procedure of exercise test was explained to the subjects and demonstrated beforehand and subjects were made to take a pretest to allay apprehension. [12]

Respiratory rate in cycles/ min: Respiratory rate in cycles/ min was recorded for three times. First before the step test, second

immediately from 15 seconds to 30 seconds after the test and third time at 5 min after the test without the knowledge of the subject. Respiratory rates were recorded as RRR, RRE and RR5 respectively.

Percent recovery respiratory rate at the end of 5 min recovery was calculated by using formula, [13]

Percent recovery respiratory rate =

$$\frac{(RRE-RR5) \times 100}{RRE-RRR}$$

RRE-RRR

Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) in lit/min: Under aseptic precautions, the subject was asked to blow forcefully after deep inspiration into the mini-Wright's.

Peak Flow meter (PEAK FLOW MASTER CIPLA MUMBAI-INDIA). The calibrations are from 60-800 liters per minute. Three readings were taken in standing position and the best was considered.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed by through SPSS for Windows (Version 16. Chicago). Unpaired 't' test & Chi-square test was used. $P > 0.05$ was considered statistically not significant (NS) and $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant (S). $P < 0.001$ was considered statistically highly significant.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of respiratory rates in cycles/min between students of medical

Parameters	Medical Education Mean \pm SD	p value
RRR	18.2 \pm 1.5	<0.001
RRE	34.6 \pm 5.8	<0.001
RR5	28.2 \pm 3.5	<0.001

The comparison of mean resting, peak exercise, and 5 min after ARST respiratory rates showed that all the differences were statistically highly significant.

Table 2: Comparison of increase in respiratory rate at the end of Astrand-Rhything Step test (ARST) and Percent recovery respiratory rate (Percent RRR) at the end of 5 min recovery after ARST over pre -test between students of medical

Increase in respiratory rate at end of ARST over pre -test			Percent recovery respiratory rate at the end of 5 min recovery after ARST over pre -test		
Medical	Education	p value	Medical	Education (Percent	p value

(RRE- RRR)		RRR)	
15.5±5.2	<0.001	42%	<0.001

The increase in respiratory rate at the end of Astrand-Rhyming Step test (ARST) and Percent recovery respiratory rate (Percent RRR) at the end of 5 min recovery after ARST over pre -test between showed significant results.

Table 3: Comparison of PEAK expiratory flow rate between students of medical

Parameter	Medical Education Mean ± SD	p value
PEFR Liters/min	460.2±66.4	<0.001

The mean PEFR±1SD in ME students was 460.2±66.4 and the difference was statistically highly significant.

Discussion

Peak expiratory flow is a measurement of the movement of air into and out of the lungs during various breathing maneuvers. [14] In effect of postural changes, lung volumes in normal subjects were significantly higher in a standing position. [15] Other studies reported that in healthy subjects spirometric indices were higher in the standing in comparison with the sitting position, [16] whereas some other studies have reported no differences between spirometric values obtained in lying, sitting, and standing positions. [17] Persson et al [18] pointed out that there is an urgency to reach a better understanding of the relationship of impaired pulmonary function to disease in order to undertake preventive measures. Buffalo health study concluded that pulmonary function is a long-term predictor for overall survival rates in both genders and could be used as a tool in general health assessment. [19]

The comparison of mean resting, peak exercise, and 5 min after ARST respiratory rates showed that all the differences were statistically highly significant. Similar increases in respiratory rate following exercise are reported in other studies also. [20,21] This is due to a rapid neurogenic component and a slower humoral component according to the neurohumoral theory of exercise hyperpnoea. As person begins to exercise the respiration increases

in depth and rate in proportion to concentration of CO₂ in blood. [22] The increase in respiratory rate at the end of Astrand-Rhyming Step test (ARST) and Percent recovery respiratory rate (Percent RRR) at the end of 5 min recovery after ARST over pre -test between showed significant results. Similar to the findings of the present study, Izedebaska E et al [23] and Khodnapur IP et al [24] also have demonstrated a significantly lower resting respiratory rates in trained young normotensive and trained residential school children respectively. Studies done by Alpert JS et al, [25] and Pierce AK et al, [26] have also reported diminished resting respiratory rate after training in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Regular aerobic training is associated with several cardiovascular, pulmonary and muscular adaptations leading to improvement in metabolic regulation. [27] These changes lead to lesser increase in respiratory rate and faster recovery of respiratory rate in trained individuals following exercise. The mean PEFR±1SD in ME students was 460.2±66.4 and the difference was statistically highly significant.. PEFR is effort dependent and also reflects the status of larger airways. [28] It is a measurement which is dependent upon several variables including airway resistance, maximal voluntary muscular effort and possible compressive effect of the maneuver on thoracic airways. [29] Aerobic training causes regular forceful inhalation and deflation of the lungs for

prolonged periods. This in turn leads to strengthening of respiratory muscles and structural changes in the airways which increase PEFV values in trained subjects. [30] No improvement of PEFV in trained subjects in the study by Hulke SM et al, [26] could be due to lesser duration and moderate degree of exercise not involving respiratory system performed by the subjects in their study.

Conclusion

The present study revealed that the important parameters of pulmonary fitness like Respiratory rates and PEFV among ME students. Beneficial effects of exercise are well known since the ancient Vedas. The present attractive education system has helped to improve the education standards, but the non-active sedentary stressful life has made the youth physically unfit. Regular physical activity is an essential part of the healthy life style and should be encouraged among medical students.

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